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Effects Of Current Conflict On Rural Household Food Security In Algoze Locality, South Kordofan State, Sudan

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ABSTRACT

The current study was conducted in Algoze locality in South Kordofan state during 2024. The study was a comparative study aimed at a comparative investigation of the effects of current conflict on rural household food security status in the study area. Study used field household survey questionnaire prepared to answer study questions, simple random sampling technique was used to select respondents. Sample size was 138 interviewed household from study population of . Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and (T) test correlation coefficient as well as Household Economy Approach . Results showed that percentage of respondents gender, 88.5% were male, 50.4% of them were farmers, 21.6% were workers and 28% were merchants, 94.2% were married, result of Household Economy Approach, showed that the average households food consumption before war was 53.29 Kg per household per week versus 43.05 Kg per household per week during war. Also the results showed that food security threshold for household before war was 2,633 kilocalories per person per day, so the person was food secured and for the households after war was 2,071 kilocalories per person per day indicating that the person was moderately food insecure. The study concluded that the war directly affected household food security situation. This needs interventions from governmental and non-governmental organizations to rectify their food security situation.

Keywords: War, household economy approach (HEA). South Kordofan, Food security

INTRODUCTION

This Study was conducted in Algoze locality in South Kordofan state, Sudan during the ongoing war in 2024. Generally speaking, food security exists when all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life. - 1996 World Food Summit From this definition, four main dimensions of food security can be identified:

Physical availability of food: Food availability addresses the “supply side” of food security and is determined by the level of food production, stock levels and net trade. Economic and physical access to food: An adequate supply of food at the national or international level does not in itself guarantee household food security level. Concerns about insufficient food access have resulted in a greater policy focus on incomes, expenditure, markets and prices in achieving food security objectives.

Food utilization: Utilization is commonly understood as the way the body makes the most of various nutrients in the food. Sufficient energy and nutrient intake by individuals is the result of good care and

feeding practices, food preparation, and diversity of diet and intra-household distribution of food. Combined with good biological utilization of food consumed, this determines the nutritional status of individuals.

Stability of the other three dimensions over time: Even if food intake is adequate today, one is still considered to be food insecure if one have inadequate access to food on a periodic basis, risking a deterioration of nutritional status. Adverse weather conditions, political instability, or economic factors (unemployment, rising food prices) may have an impact on food security status.

For food security objectives to be realized, all four dimensions must be fulfilled simultaneously.

The concept of seasonal food security falls between chronic and transitory food insecurity. It is similar to chronic food insecurity as it is usually predictable and follows a sequence of known events. However, as seasonal food insecurity is of limited duration it can also be seen as recurrent, transitory food insecurity. It occurs when there is a cyclical pattern of inadequate availability and access to food. This is associated with seasonal fluctuations in the climate, cropping patterns, work opportunities (labour demand) and disease. (FAO, 2008)

Food insecurity affects the lives of millions of people across the world and is increasingly concentrated in conflict-affected regions. All 19 countries FAO currently classifies as being in a protracted food crisis are also currently affected by conflict and violence (Holleman *et al.*, 2017). Globally, 60 percent of the 815 million undernourished individuals and 79 percent of the 155 million stunted children live in countries affected by violent conflicts (FAO *et al.*, 2017).

There are clear links between high prices, lower calorie intake, lower quality diet, and increase in child malnutrition (Alderman, *et al.* 2006). Tiwari and Zaman (2010) found that the 2008 global food price spike increased global undernourishment by 6.8 percent, or 63 million people. Volatile prices lead to food insecurity that can lead to conflict. At the same time, conflict can also lead to price volatility. Maize prices in Kenya, driven by lower plantings from election-related disruptions, higher fertilizer prices, and a drought, rose even during the latter part of 2008 when global prices were falling (World Bank 2010a).

Conflict destroys land, water, biological, and social resources for food production. Thirty million people in more than 60 countries were displaced or had their livelihoods destroyed by conflict every year in the 1990s (WFP, 2004). FAO (2002) has estimated losses of almost \$52 billion in agricultural output through conflict in Sub-Saharan Africa between 1970 and 1997, a figure equivalent to 75 % of all official development assistance received by the conflict-affected countries. Estimated losses for all developing countries averaged \$4.3 billion per year – enough to have raised the food intake of 330 million undernourished people to minimum required levels. Military expenditures lower investments in health, education, agriculture and environmental protection. In the late 1990s and early 2000s, low and middle-income countries devoted nearly 13 percent of government budgets to defense (Messer and Cohen, 2006).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data resources, primary data were collected via field house hold questionnaire to interview selected households, secondary data were collected from similar previous studies and relevant researches, sampling and sample size: simple random sampling technique was used to select respondents, $n = z^2(p)(1-p)/d$. Sample size was 139 interviewed household from study population Descriptive statistics, Correlation analysis, T test and Household Economy Approach (HEA) were used for food security analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It seems plausible that demographic data on respondents under study for their food security, especially under security unrest, is preferable. In this study, results showed that 57% of the respondents were female, and 43% were male. Moreover, 57.4%, 28% and 21.6% of the interviewed respondents were farmers, merchants and other employee; respectively (Table 1). Majorities (94%) of the farmers were married (Table 2). As presented in Table3, table (6) the average weekly household food consumption and expenditure before war 53.2 kg food materials with cost SDG 41, 588, as compared with 43.05 kg with

cost of SDG 34,807 during war time. . Also the results of household economy approach showed that food security threshold for household before war was 2,633 kilocalories per person per day, so the person was food secured and for the households after war was 2,071 kilocalories per person per day so the person was moderately food insecure.

Significant difference was detected between household weekly food expenditure before and during war ($t = -8.263$, $df. 138$, $P \leq 0.000$). That is, household food expenditure significantly increased during the current conflict where food commodities prices are escalated to unprecedented levels due to scarcity and increase in their prices due to high cost of transportation and the risks of looting. Trucks carrying food commodities tend to take longer routes to avoid RSF checkpoints where they either confiscate the consignment or ask for ransom for both commodity and truck. It was clear that households consume less amount of food during war, but pay more money (SDG 244,755), when compared to the payment before war (SDG 113,786), due to inflation rate that equals 215%. Inflation rate in study area was less than inflation rate in South Kordofan State and more than the general inflation rate of the Sudan (193.7%). Study concluded that the war affect households income, expenditure, livestock and crop production wood products revenues and hence affected food security situation. Strategies and new technologies recommended mitigating the impact of war in the study area. Table (1) reveals the respondent's jobs kind, resulted 50.4% were farmers, 21.6% were workers and 28% were merchants.

Table (1) Respondent occupations in the study area

Occupation	Frequent	Percentage
Farmer	70	50.4
Merchant	39	28
Employee	30	21.6
Total	139	100

Source: Filed survey 2024

Table (2) respondent's mean age, family size and gender, 57% were female, 43% were mail.

Table: 4. Mean age and family size

Items	Before war		In war time	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	41	10.76	36	12.38
Size of family	7	2.20	6	2.20
Male	3	1.58	3	1.58
Female	4	1.71	3	1.58

Source: Filed survey, 2024

Table (3) Food Security Situation; Household Weekly Food Consumption and Expenditure in the study area

Food Item	Before war			During current war		
	Quant. cons. /Kg.	Price/SD G /Kg.	Total Cos./SDG	Quant. cons. /Kg.	Price/SDG /Kg.	Total Cos./SDG
Millet	7.00	666	4662	5.00	9300	4900
Sorghum	7.10	453	3216	5.80	6462	2627.4
Wheat	4.72	171	807	4.99	3029	853.29
meat	2.83	2,225	6297	1.83	6105	4071.75
Milk	7.10	392	2783	4.60	1189	1803.2
sugar	3.88	1,017	3946	2.78	3236	2827.26
Tea	1.34	1,443	1918	1.16	6496	1673.88
coffee	1.24	1,531	1898	1.01	11758	1546.31
onion	4.80	889	4267	4.18	4969	3716.02
Oil	1.00	986	986	0.84	2893	828.24
Salt	2.84	737	2093	2.68	8214	1975.16
okra	1.08	3,746	4046	1.09	21065	4083.14
fruits	3.18	562	1787	2.91	2623	1635.42
vegetables	1.55	454	704	1.66	4838	753.64
macaroni	3.63	600	2178	2.52	2054	1512
total	53.29		41,588	43.054		34,806.71

Source: H.H survey (2024)

Table (4) Average weekly household food items consumption and expenditure in adult equivalent in the study area

Food Item	Before war		During war	
	Quant. cons. /Kg. before war	Total k.cal consumed before war	Quant. cons. in kg. during war	Total k. cal. Consumed during war
Millet	7.00	23,450	5.00	16,750
Sorghum	7.10	23,785	5.80	19,430
Wheat	4.72	15,670	4.99	16,566
meat	2.83	5,717	1.83	3,697
milk	7.10	4,686	4.60	3,036
sugar	3.88	15,520	2.78	11,120
Tea	1.34	0	1.16	0
coffee	1.24	0	1.01	0
onion	4.80	1,968	4.18	1,714
Oil	1.00	8,840	0.84	7,426
salt	2.84	0	2.68	0
okra	1.08	378	1.09	382
Fruits / dates	3.18	6,614	2.91	6,053
vegetables	1.55	310	1.66	332
macaroni	3.63	20,000	2.52	14,975
Total/H-H/W	53.29	147,440	43.054	101,481
Per/H-H/Day		21,063		14,5
Per/person/Day		2,633		2,071

Source: H.H survey (2024)

Table (8) shows significant deference between household's average weekly food expenditure, before and during war. (T) test probability value of (T) equal(-8.263), which is less than the significant value level (0.000), therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis at (0.05), therefore the study concluded that the average weekly household food expenditure before war was less than that during war, and the total household weekly food expenditure was more than within war time.

Table (8) the result of T test for the independent two samples correlation and the deference between the weekly household food expenditure before and during war

T test	Degree of freedom	Number	averages		Sig value
			before	during	
-8.263	138	139	41588.08	192949.65	0.000

SPSS.V23 analysis output 2024

Result of correlation analysis, significant differences between the average weekly household food items consumption before and during war in study area.

Table (9) showed significant difference between average weekly household food items consumption before and during war. (T) Test probability value of (T) equal (6.638), which is more than the significant value level (0.000), so we reject the null-hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis at (0.05), we concluded that the average weekly household food consumption before war was more than that during war.

Table (9) average weekly household food items consumption before ware and during war correlation.

T test	Degree of freedom	Number	Average food items consumption		Sig value
			before	during	
6.638	137	138	53.29	43.054	0.000

SPSS.V23 analysis output 2024

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion:-

The study concluded that the war has affected rural household food security in study area, average weekly household food expenditure before was less than during war, and the total weekly food expenditure is increasing during war, food security situation before war was classified food secured and moderately food insecure after war. Average cost of food items during war and household's food consumption has decreased.

Recommendation:

- Comprehensive economic development strategies, footing stone for peace and sustainable development
- Food aid and income generation activities interventions.
- Strategies and new technologies recommended as solutions to mitigate effects of war on food security in study area.

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